

Dementia-Inclusive Travel: Perspectives of Specialist Travel Service Providers

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Abstract

This paper explores the experiences and perspectives of travel experts who provide services to people living with dementia and their care partners. The study aims to identify the challenges and effective strategies for creating inclusive travel opportunities in this context. The findings are based solely on the perspectives of service providers and do not include direct input from individuals living with dementia or their care partners. A qualitative research design was adopted, involving in-depth interviews with six participants who possess extensive experience in facilitating travel for individuals with dementia. Due to the small number of operators in this niche, participants were selected based on relevant experience in dementia-inclusive tourism. The interview questions explored strategies used by the travel experts to support travellers with dementia, perceived barriers and challenges, and recommendations for tourism operators developing dementia-inclusive services. Data were analysed thematically to identify recurring patterns and insights. Four major themes emerged: (1) enabling tourism services; (2) logistics of enabling services; (3) fostering bonds and purpose; and (4) travel as a key factor to living well. These findings highlight the importance of tailored support and inclusive practices in creating positive travel experiences. This research contributes to the growing body of literature on dementia-inclusive travel by deepening understanding of how travel experiences can be made more accessible, enjoyable, and supportive for people living with dementia and their care partners. The insights can inform tourism, hospitality, healthcare professionals, and host communities by deepening understanding of this growing tourist segment and guiding more inclusive support and services.

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1. Introduction

“Living well” is increasingly embraced by older adults and those with (dis)abilities, acknowledging that health is shaped by physical, cognitive, emotional, social, and environmental factors (Martyr et al., 2018). Ageing and conditions like dementia do not mean that quality of life experiences need necessarily decline. For many, living well includes recreation and travel, which support cognitive and emotional well-being. Engaging in tourism and physical activity can stimulate neurological function and offer meaningful experiences for people with dementia. When guided by dementia specialists, such tourism experiences may serve as valuable non-pharmacological interventions (Wen et al., 2022). While there is emerging literature addressing dementia-inclusive travel, particularly in the context of enhancing the inclusivity of airports and other transport hubs (O’Reilly & Shepherd, 2016; Warren et al., 2022), there remains a notable gap concerning the development of dementia-inclusive travel experiences more broadly.

Global initiatives such as the World Health Organisation’s (WHO) *Global Strategy and Action Plan on Ageing and Health* and *The United Nations Decade of Healthy Ageing: Plan for Action 2021–2030* reflect growing efforts to support health in later life (WHO, 2017; UN, 2020; Hu et al., 2023). Tourism is increasingly recognised for its positive physical, psychological, and social impacts on older adults (Vega-Vazquez et al., 2021; Patterson & Balderas-Cejudo, 2023), offering opportunities for activity, interaction, and overall well-being (Wen et al., 2022; Chang et al., 2022). Specific forms of tourism, such as spa and social tourism, align with positive ageing ideals (Koskinen, 2019; Morgan et al., 2015). These experiences can potentially enhance quality of life and healthy living and help to overcome social isolation and loneliness (Knobloch et al., 2017). With more leisure time, spending power, and interest in travel, older adults represent a growing tourist segment (Patterson et al., 2021), driving demand for age-friendly services (Li & Chan, 2021). Yet, the industry has been slow to respond (Pan et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2022; Hu et al., 2023). While dementia-inclusive services are gaining attention, Field et al. (2021) caution that poorly designed initiatives may unintentionally reinforce stigma, particularly when individuals are grouped based on the stage of their condition.

Dementia-inclusive tourism supports global sustainability agendas, particularly the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 3: Good Health and Well-being and SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities), by addressing health-related needs and promoting equal opportunities in tourism, making dementia-inclusive travel not only a commercial consideration but also an ethical imperative that reflects the social responsibility of tourism providers. Participants in this study were experienced travel providers from the United Kingdom (UK) and the United States (US) who support dementia-inclusive travel. Their insights are particularly relevant to destinations where comparable dementia-supportive tourism services are often scarce.

The primary aim of this research was to generate insights and practical strategies that could inform the

tourism industry's efforts to implement dementia-inclusive travel offerings, including supported holiday experiences. It is hoped that these insights will contribute towards the development of a more dementia-inclusive tourism industry in emerging destinations by facilitating the development and ongoing provision of positive travel experiences for people living with dementia.

1.1. The impact of dementia

Dementia refers to a group of serious, progressive conditions that impair cognitive functions such as memory, language, and judgement, often leading to loss of independence and reduced quality of life for both individuals and their care partners (Isik et al., 2019). The disease trajectory tends to occur in three stages: mild or early-stage dementia; moderate or middle-stage dementia; and severe or late-stage dementia (Dementia Australia, 2022). While not caused by ageing, its prevalence increases with age, making it a growing global concern. Due to limited pharmacological treatments, non-pharmacological approaches to care, such as music therapy, validation, and environmental adaptations, are preferred for promoting well-being (Meyer & O'Keefe, 2020; Ross et al., 2023).

Caring for someone with dementia can be emotionally and physically demanding, and it can be stressful to travel with someone who has dementia. This can lead to lost leisure opportunities and caregiver fatigue (Hu et al., 2023). However, with the right support, it can be a very positive experience for travel companions, as well as the person with dementia (O'Reilly & Shephard, 2016). Engaging in tourism with care recipients might offer the care partner relief from their responsibilities or contribute to positive bonding experiences between the two (Maayan et al., 2014). Calls have been made for more inclusive and holistic tourism services to meet these needs (Bauer, 2019; Connell & Page, 2019), yet research on dementia-inclusive travel remains limited.

1.2. Dementia and tourism management

Most research on dementia-inclusive travel is focused on Europe and the UK, where policies support dementia-inclusive communities and leisure participation (Innes et al., 2016). Dementia poses unique challenges for the tourism industry (Hayden et al., 2022), including the need to address staff and community stereotypes. Hotels, for instance, could act as hubs for social and health support by offering dementia-trained staff, on-call specialists, and external caregivers (Blanas et al., 2016). In Taiwan, a participatory action research project involved staff of a tourism venture and dementia experts in the development of a dementia-inclusive destination experience. The project highlighted the importance of first understanding different stakeholders' perspectives and values before designing and implementing the programs that could impact the broader community (Wu & Sung, 2021).

Recent efforts have focused on making airports and air travel more dementia-inclusive (O'Reilly & Shepherd, 2016; Warren et al., 2022), while the UK has worked to adapt heritage sites, museums, and galleries as part of broader dementia-inclusive community initiatives (Klug et al., 2017). Considerations for establishing dementia-inclusive physical environments include layout, consistent signage, good lighting, use of contrasting colours, avoidance of highly patterned surfaces, and accessible and easy-to-find toilets (Fleming et al., 2022; Mathews et al., 2021). There are also opportunities to create products like memory cafés, dementia-inclusive respite accommodation, and themed restaurants that raise dementia awareness, such as Japan's Restaurant of Mistaken Orders (Hayden et al., 2022). Architectural hybrids, exemplified by the Dementia Village® (2024), combine urban design, healthcare provision, and hospitality to create inclusive environments that support ageing and travel for people with dementia and their companions (Chrysikou et al., 2017). Despite growing recognition of dementia-inclusive practices within tourism and hospitality research, the existing literature remains fragmented and largely centred on physical accessibility, transport hubs, or isolated case studies of dementia-friendly initiatives (O'Reilly & Shepherd, 2016; Warren et al., 2022; Wu & Sung, 2021). Much of the current literature adopts a service or environmental design perspective, often overlooking how tourism participation is shaped by intersecting motivational, social, and support-related factors. Furthermore, there is limited empirical research drawing on the experiences of specialist dementia-inclusive travel providers, despite these providers possessing practical expertise regarding the barriers, support mechanisms, and service adaptations required to facilitate meaningful travel experiences. This study addresses this gap by examining dementia-inclusive tourism through the perspectives of specialist providers in the UK and US and by identifying practical strategies that can support the development of more inclusive tourism experiences in emerging destinations.

1.3. Aim of the study

Making tourism destinations accessible upholds the rights of people with disabilities and enhances service quality and business opportunities (United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 2006; World Tourism Organisation, 2024). Internet searches reveal numerous businesses that provide inclusive tourism opportunities; however, businesses primarily cater to people with physical disabilities. Dementia-specific travel services are rare and found mainly in the UK and the US, with limited research on their benefits (Mapes, 2017). To explore how the tourism industry can better support travellers with dementia, we consulted specialist service providers to ask: (a) How can the needs of travellers with dementia be best addressed? and (b) What advice can help tourism operators develop dementia-inclusive experiences? The findings of this study were explored through the lens of the push–pull tourist motivation model, which offers a framework for understanding both traveller motivations and destination attributes (Crompton, 1979). The model was selected because dementia-inclusive travel involves not only motivations associated with

leisure and well-being, but also considerations relating to safety, familiarity, accessibility, emotional comfort, and support services. As such, the framework enables examination of how both personal and environmental factors influence travel experiences for people living with dementia and their companions. Although the push–pull model has been widely applied in tourism research, its relevance to dementia-inclusive tourism has received limited attention. This study extends the framework by demonstrating that, within the context of cognitive decline and supported travel, motivations and constraints are not fixed or stable but continually negotiated over time. Rather than conceptualising travel decisions solely through destination attraction and motivation, the findings suggest that dementia-related travel participation is shaped by the dynamic interaction between constraining forces and enabling supports. In doing so, the study broadens the applicability of the push–pull framework to a previously underexplored tourism cohort and offers a more relational and adaptive understanding of dementia-inclusive travel.

2. Methods

2.1. Study design and research participants

To gain a deeper understanding of travel experts' perspectives and insights, this study used a constructivist epistemology and qualitative design, focusing on the subjective experiences of providers of dementia-friendly tourism services. We conducted interviews with service providers specialising in inclusive tourism for people living with dementia, identified through internet searches and professional networks, and invited them via email to participate in one-on-one videoconference interviews. Given the limited number of operators in this niche field, participants were recruited using purposive sampling to ensure inclusion of specialist providers with direct experience in dementia-inclusive travel services. A total of six individuals (five female, one male) with substantial expertise in supporting the travel needs of people with dementia and their care partners participated. Their diverse professional backgrounds and perspectives are summarised in Table 1 (participants are identified by pseudonyms). All were either from the UK or the USA.

Although based on insights from UK and US travel experts, the findings are relevant to other destinations due to ageing populations globally. While local differences may exist, the key themes are widely applicable and transferable and align with the global movement toward dementia-inclusive communities. The adoption and adaptation of international examples contribute to the shared goal of enhancing participation and quality of life for people living with dementia.

Tourism operators in developing destinations can draw on these international insights and tailor them to local conditions, including policy frameworks, geographic considerations, and cultural nuances.

Table 1: Pseudonyms of research participants and their area of expertise

Pseudonym	Broad background and area of expertise	Location
Pat	Legal background working with older adults and currently runs travel companion service.	USA
Alice	Nursing background working with older adults and people with dementia, currently is a consultant, advocate and author.	USA
Linda	Aviation background supporting customer service, and currently an advocate for people with hidden disabilities.	UK
Jill	Health and social care background in working with people with dementia, currently working for travel provider for people living with dementia.	UK
Jane	Nursing background, currently working for a travel provider for people living with dementia.	UK
Peter	Background in aviation and local government, currently an academic, author and advocate for people living with dementia.	UK

2.2. Recruitment and interview protocol

Expert interview participants were recruited through targeted invitations via existing contacts within the research team and internet searches of relevant agencies. Six interviews were conducted between October and December 2021, each lasting 30–60 minutes. The interviews explored travel professionals’ strategies for supporting people living with dementia, their perceptions of key barriers and challenges, and their recommendations for developing dementia-inclusive tourism services. Participants also reflected on their own motivations, experiences, and views on broader systemic issues. Saturation was considered achieved when no substantially new themes, concepts, or practical insights emerged in the later interviews, consistent with Guest et al.’s (2006) observation that thematic saturation in focused qualitative studies is often evident by the sixth interview.

2.3. Data analysis

The interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim, followed by an inductive content analysis (Elo et al., 2014). The analysis proceeded through a systematic multi-stage coding process. First, transcripts were independently read several times by two members of the research team to ensure familiarity with the data. Open coding was then conducted independently by these two researchers, involving line-by-line coding to identify and label meaningful units of text. These initial codes were compared and discussed to identify overlaps, differences, and areas of agreement, resulting in a preliminary agreed coding framework. In the second stage, axial coding was undertaken to examine relationships between codes and to group them into higher-order categories based on conceptual similarity and emerging patterns. Finally, selective coding was used to refine and integrate these categories into overarching themes and subthemes that best represented the dataset.

Trustworthiness was enhanced using Decrop’s (2004) criteria of credibility and transferability. Credibility was established through independent coding by two researchers, followed by iterative comparison, discussion, and consensus, with the full research team reviewing and validating the final thematic structure. Transferability was supported through rich description and the use of illustrative participant quotations to contextualise and ground the findings.

2.4. Ethical considerations

Research involving travellers living with dementia presents distinct methodological challenges and ethical considerations. However, it is important to clarify that the present study focuses on interviews with travel experts who provide tourism experiences for people with dementia as the primary subject of analysis. Prior to commencing the study, ethical approval was obtained from the [university removed for peer review] Human Research Ethics Committee (#22613). Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they fully understood the purpose, scope, and voluntary nature of their involvement.

3. Findings

Four major themes were identified from the transcripts: (1) *enabling tourism services*; (2) *logistics of enabling services*; (3) *fostering bonds and purpose*; and (4) *travel as a key factor to living well* (see Table 2). While some of the themes are interconnecting and overlapping, they are each explored separately to understand how organisations can support people with dementia and their care partners to travel and better understand the benefits to clients as perceived by those offering services to them.

Table 2: Major themes and their subthemes outlining factors influencing and supporting dementia-inclusive travel

Enabling tourism services	Logistics of enabling services	Fostering bonds and purpose	Travel as a key factor in living well
Companion services	Well-connected travel providers	Family connection and support	Pleasure and stimulation
Supported holiday provision	Assessment of needs and changing needs	Social health	Physical activity
Dementia-inclusive training		Making a difference	Empowerment
Advocacy			Respite for care partner

3.1. Enabling travel services

Participants discussed four subthemes of support services: *companion services*, *supported holiday provision*,

dementia-inclusive training, and *advocacy*. These services function to reduce structural and relational barriers to travel participation, thereby enabling safe, meaningful, and dignified travel experiences for people living with dementia and their care partners. While most services operate within user-pays or funded models, volunteer involvement also plays a significant role, reflecting a hybrid service ecosystem. Importantly, participants framed these supports not as optional add-ons, but as essential enablers of inclusion, autonomy, and “living well” through travel.

Companion services support travellers with dementia across the travel journey, particularly in high-complexity environments such as airports and transit hubs, though some services extend to full-trip accompaniment. As Pat explained, “*Sometimes people just want me to take them to a destination and drop them off.*” These services enable travel without reliance on family members, supporting independence and reducing caregiver burden, while still ensuring safety and continuity of support. Informal equivalents were also acknowledged through family-based assistance.

Supported holiday provision involve curated travel packages for people living with dementia and their care partners, including accommodation, activities, and care support. Jane explained, “*We run these holidays every year, for people living with dementia and their family carer. So, it’s all the planning, sorting suitable itineraries, that sort of thing.*” These experiences range from group travel to bespoke family holidays, as illustrated by a tailored coastal trip designed to accommodate a younger family unit. Jane provided an example of the latter:

I got approached by a lady, she was in her late forties with two children and a husband living with dementia. Last year they managed to get away through a caravan with another family so that the children at least had a holiday, but she never got a break and was struggling with her husband stuck in the caravan. This year, I set up a bespoke family holiday. They went for a week to the coast as a family with one of our adventure leaders and one of our experienced volunteers. They went bodyboarding as a family with the dad and our team on the beach, and it meant that she could enjoy some time with the children, knowing that he was safe.

This quote highlights the additional considerations for younger people living with dementia, whose travel plans may need to accommodate children. While group holidays may suit couples or individuals with a companion, they are often less appropriate for families. The vignette highlights that travel for people with dementia is frequently a family matter rather than an individual one.

Dementia-inclusive training was identified as critical to building sector capability and standardising

service quality. Participants emphasised structured programmes for staff, volunteers, and travel companions. For some, training helps raise quality and consistency across providers. As Pat noted, *“I train people to do this job ... to put together workshops and certify people, so then there’s some standards in this new industry.”* Alice also stressed the need for ongoing training to support growth in this emerging field:

We are going to offer a certification program (for travel companions) that is a two-days plus. Our plans are that it’ll be an intensive couple of days, and then we’re going to give them homework where they have to apply and plan. Thus program is important for ensuring the next generation of people carry on this work.

Training formats ranged from intensive workshops to brief digital resources, reflecting scalability and accessibility considerations. Jill stated:

We’ve created a two-day training package. We do have volunteers from around the UK. They spend a day talking about dementia and what the holidays mean, what it really consists of to be a volunteer on holiday. And the second day is first aid.

In addition to formal training sessions, Linda acknowledged that training can also take place through other channels: *“We have three training videos. They’re just over two minutes in length each. We are very conscious that training costs time and money. It just says, ‘This customer has a non-visible disability. How can I help you today?’”* In some cases, training was also offered to family and friends to support dementia care partners, especially when travel or time away from home was involved. These sessions equipped carers with practical tools and confidence to enable enriching and manageable travel experiences. Jill provided several examples:

We have a session called ‘Thinking differently about dementia’. We’ve sessions called ‘Mood and motivation’, because often that is an issue. Then we have a session called ‘Nature is calling’ where we help people look at their barriers to getting outside. There’s lots of strategies available (...) we’re helping people to live the best life.

Advocacy was positioned as a foundational activity underpinning service development and societal change. Participants highlighted the need to challenge exclusionary assumptions about travel capability following diagnosis. As Peter explained:

There are 850,000 people in the UK with dementia. Why should you stop doing something that you love, just because you’ve been diagnosed with something? We need to be enabling people to do it. To people in the airlines and the airports, that is 850,000 people who still might want to travel. And what we’ve got to do is make sure that they can do that.

Advocacy efforts included industry education, awareness raising, and symbolic tools such as the sunflower lanyard. As Linda said: *“My job is to raise awareness with businesses and organisations across the world.”* Alice noted the need *“to raise awareness that older people do travel... And we have to ensure that people*

have the right and the ability to travel.” Pat was passionate about making travel easier for those living with dementia: *“I use it (Sunflower lanyard) as an educational tool. So when I’m going through the airport and I will stop and tell the (staff) if there’s time, that there’s somebody here that’s got a lanyard on, and this is what it means.”*

Overall, these findings demonstrate that dementia-inclusive travel extends beyond accessibility-focused service provision and instead operates through flexible and co-produced forms of support. The identified services show how autonomy and participation are often enabled through structured assistance, professional support, and collaborative care practices. Furthermore, the emphasis on training and advocacy suggests that dementia-inclusive tourism is transitioning from an informal and fragmented practice towards a more professionalised and rights-based approach, where travel participation is increasingly framed as a matter of dignity, inclusion, and social citizenship rather than solely leisure consumption.

3.2. Logistics of enabling services

This theme focuses on the logistics of running services that support the travel goals of people living with dementia and their care partners to ensure their travel needs are met. Rather than being purely functional, these logistics reflect a dynamic system of coordination, responsiveness, and adaptation. Two subthemes emerged: *well-connected travel providers* and *assessment of needs and changing needs*.

Well-connected travel providers are central to the implementation and sustainability of dementia-inclusive services, with relational networks functioning as a form of operational capital. Strong partnerships enable providers to mobilise resources that are not typically embedded within standard tourism offerings. As Jane explained: *We’ve built really good relationships with the accommodation providers, and they are then prepared to work with us. They’ll go and buy raised toilet seats for us and store them somewhere.*” Similarly, Jill mentioned: *“We make connections with the local carers’ groups. We often do training with them so that... the carers’ group can tell people what’s available locally.”* All of those interviewed were highly connected to a wide range of organisations, including dementia organisations, healthcare systems, transport providers, government bodies, and community groups. This interconnectedness suggests that dementia-inclusive tourism is not delivered by isolated actors but emerges from collaborative ecosystems that span sectors.

A second defining feature across all services was the need for a comprehensive ***assessment of needs and changing needs***. This process extends beyond initial screening to an ongoing evaluative practice that acknowledges the fluctuating nature of dementia. Pat explained: *“There’s a lot of communication. I’ll ask*

them specific questions. People are pretty honest about saying, you know, mild or moderate (dementia)." Providers must assess clients both before and during the holiday. As Jane noted:

We do a quite comprehensive assessment, over the telephone or Zoom, to make sure that the holiday is going to be suitable. We assess them before they go. We always do it the week before to check that nothing has changed.

This highlights an anticipatory approach that seeks to minimise risk while maintaining client participation. Alice's reflection points to structural gaps within the broader tourism industry:

I've tried to see if I could do some things through the travel agent industry. Even though they book travel for older people, it's amazing the reluctance to assess further unique needs, such as slow thinkers and slow walkers. So, is there a way that you can say, 'Are you travelling with somebody who maybe processes information a little slower?'

This suggests that current industry practices are constrained by stigma and a lack of nuanced assessment frameworks, limiting their capacity to respond inclusively. In addition, the unpredictable nature of travel requires ongoing assessment flexibility. Jill shared:

Every evening, the adventure leader and the volunteers write a daily report. I check if they're having any problems and I contact them to find out if they need me to book something else. I think when you're on holiday, you've got your hands full, so the office is there to back that up.

Service adaptations based on user feedback demonstrate a shift toward personalised and dignity-preserving solutions. For example, while some may be more hesitant to wear the Sunflower lanyard, they might prefer wearing a pin or wristband. The Hidden Disabilities Sunflower is a discreet symbol used to indicate that someone may need extra support or patience in public spaces (Hidden Disabilities Sunflower, 2024).

Linda sought feedback from a carers' group shortly after the lanyard's launch to better tailor its use:

One lady said to me, 'We used to travel so much before my husband was diagnosed, but he will not wear the lanyard'. And that's how we came up with the pin badge. So, the pin badge is another option and there's a wristband and various bits and pieces now. It's about getting feedback from people.

The findings show that dementia-inclusive travel depends not only on individual service adjustments but also on coordinated networks, sustained relationships, and flexible responses to changing needs. The importance placed on partnerships and cross-sector collaboration highlights that dementia-inclusive tourism operates as a collaborative care ecosystem rather than a standalone tourism service. Ongoing assessment reflects the unpredictable nature of dementia, requiring providers to move beyond standardised tourism models towards personalised and adaptive approaches. Persistent stigma influences interactions and disclosure, highlighting the need for more inclusive communication.

3.3. Fostering bonds and purpose

Participants described how travel creates opportunities for thriving together, building bonds and fostering a sense of purpose. This theme includes three subthemes: *family connections and support*; *social health*; and *travel providers making a difference*.

The participants reflected on how travel has become an essential part of ***family connections and support*** for many. As noted in the literature, transit challenges, like navigating airports, can result in separation from loved ones, negatively impacting quality of life. Pat shared the joy of helping reunite families:

I received a letter from this one woman whose mother moved in with her and she said, 'I had my mum with me for six months before she passed, and I wouldn't have been able to have that time unless you made that happen for me'. And she was just so thankful.

This illustrates how travel functions as an enabler of relational closure and memory-making, particularly at later stages of life. Similarly, for couples, travel was described as a way to preserve relational identities beyond caregiver–care recipient roles. Jane recalled one woman saying: “*I just want to go on holiday with the man I love, but I need some support to do it.*”

Travel providers also play a critical role in fostering ***social health***, extending their impact beyond the temporal boundaries of travel itself.

This became clear during the COVID-19 pandemic, when providers adapted their services to maintain social connection despite mobility restrictions. Several providers pivoted to alternative forms of connection, using videoconferencing and phone calls to stay engaged with clients. Alice ran webinars on the impact of social isolation: “*...especially our older adults and people living with dementia.*”

Jane noted that video calls helped build relationships: “*We got some really good relationships going... there was mutual support.*”

One organisation even mobilised volunteers to call clients whose trips were cancelled.

As Jill shared: *“They were calling people that wanted a call, on a regular basis. And I think that was a real lifeline for quite a few people.”* These efforts reflect an altruistic and holistic approach, showing how these organisations look beyond economic outcomes to support the broader well-being of their clients.

A strong sense of purpose and values-driven motivation underpins the work of those delivering dementia-inclusive travel services. Participants framed their involvement in terms of ***making a difference***, reflecting a moral rather than purely commercial orientation. Jane remarked: *“All our staff and our volunteers are doing it because they’re sort of ‘want to make a difference’ type people.”* Jill contributed: *“I thought, actually, I could do something here that would be quite meaningful and hopefully help a lot of people.”* Interviewees from the UK shared national-level initiatives making a broad impact. Linda, for example, serves on the UK Prime Minister’s Air Transport Dementia Working Group, which helped introduce the Sunflower lanyard and push for more dementia-inclusive policies in airports. Peter stated that *“the Civil Aviation Authority started to think about how they were going to do things and developed some documents on guidance around quality standards for people with hidden disabilities.”*

These findings show that dementia-inclusive travel goes beyond leisure participation, supporting relationships, identity, and social connectedness. Travel is framed as a relational experience that fosters family cohesion and shared meaning amid cognitive decline, rather than an individual activity. Providers adopt holistic, care-oriented approaches that extend beyond commercial tourism, as seen in their responses during the COVID-19 pandemic. The emphasis on “making a difference” highlights values of empathy, advocacy, and social contribution. As a result, dementia-inclusive tourism positions providers not only as service facilitators but also as agents of social support and broader systemic change.

3.4. Travel as a key factor to living well

Participants indicated that tourism services should aim to benefit people living with dementia and their care partners, while they also reflected on observed benefits such as enhanced well-being and social connection. Across the interviews, travel emerged as a major theme in promoting well-being with four subthemes: *pleasure and stimulation; physical improvement; empowerment; and (for care partners) respite.*

A key motivation for travel is to seek new experiences or revisit familiar places, both of which are ***pleasurable and stimulating***. Alice acknowledged that sometimes these experiences have been deferred due to work and family commitments, but when faced with a diagnosis of dementia, they resurfaced:

We explore with them what’s most important to them in the coming year or so. And travel always bubbled up to be one of the things that people had wanted to do, but they had stalled it because of work or whatever.

For those living with dementia who experience limited short-term memory, travel can still be pleasurable

in the moment and enjoyable in retrospect, particularly through photographs, even when the memory of the event itself fades. Alice, being the voice of someone with dementia, reflected:

So, whether I have abilities to remember on my own or whether I can just look back at a picture and go, 'Isn't that nice?' Those to me are the things that stand out as I look at the quality of life for people who are ageing.

Participants also described how travel, particularly being more **physically active** outdoors, can generate temporary yet meaningful physical and cognitive improvements. Jane observed: “*We do see almost 100% of increased appetite, better sleep, more activity. Those things are valuable to the person living with dementia, but they're valuable to the carer as well because, you know, they're getting more rest.*” Jill recalled this example of temporary physical and cognitive improvement during a supported sailing holiday:

We have seen some amazing physical changes during the holiday, but they are often quite short-lived. One gentleman whose verbal expression was limited to words, not sentences, he'd been a sailor all his life, indicated to his son he wanted to wrap the sails and put them away. They harnessed him on. Up he went. He very proficiently put the sails away, came down, and was speaking in full sentences. It decreased over a half-hour period.

Participants also framed supported travel as **empowering**, particularly when it encouraged people living with dementia and their care partners to maintain engagement with the outside world beyond the holiday itself. Jill explained:

I think one of the main things for me, and we talk about this in training, is the support to get back outside again. So, we're not only empowering the couple in the moment of the holiday. We're empowering them to think about the rest of the year and we also link them to other organisations that can help them.

This subtheme of empowerment reflects both a renewed sense of confidence in individual abilities and a broader call to reduce structural and societal barriers that limit people with dementia from living well and fully participating in everyday life.

While most of the subthemes discussed apply to both people living with dementia and their care partners, the final subtheme of **respite** is specific to the care partners' experience. Caring for someone with dementia can be physically, emotionally, and mentally exhausting, especially when family support is limited. In such cases, care partners are often faced with the difficult choice of forgoing a holiday altogether or placing their loved one in respite care. Jane described how supported holidays offer a meaningful alternative:

They don't have to do the thinking, because we give them the itinerary. We drive them. We feed them. We are with them all day. We laugh with them. We cry with them. There's always tears on holiday and that's not a bad thing.

By relieving care partners of the burden of planning and decision-making, supported holidays allow them to rest, relax, and reconnect with their loved ones, turning travel into a restorative and shared experience rather than an additional source of stress.

These findings position travel as more than recreation, highlighting its role in supporting people to live well with dementia. Participants described tourism experiences as facilitating emotional stimulation, physical activity, empowerment, and relational well-being, functioning as meaningful non-pharmacological support. The results challenge deficit-based views by showing how individuals continue to experience joy, agency, and connection through supported travel. Benefits also extend to caregivers, with respite enhancing the broader care relationship. Overall, dementia-inclusive tourism supports quality of life by reinforcing identity, confidence, and social participation, while sustaining continuity in meaningful life experiences beyond momentary enjoyment.

4. Discussion

To address the first research question, interviews with travel experts provided insights into how tourism services can better support travellers with dementia and their care partners. The findings highlight the importance of *enabling services*, particularly during complex travel stages such as air travel, where anxiety, confusion, and fear of becoming lost are common concerns (Peterson et al., 2020; Peterson et al., 2024). Companion services, specialised support personnel, and dementia-aware staff were identified as central to reducing these barriers. Consistent with previous research (Page et al., 2015; Blanas et al., 2016), the study shows that dementia-inclusive tourism requires providers to move beyond standardised service delivery and instead adopt adaptive approaches that recognise changing cognitive needs.

The findings therefore contribute theoretically by positioning dementia-inclusive tourism as a dynamic and relational process rather than a fixed accessibility outcome. Participants also acted as advocates and champions within their organisations, suggesting that inclusion is shaped not only through policy, but also through individual agency and leadership within tourism systems.

The study further demonstrates, via the theme of *logistics of enabling services*, that dementia-inclusive travel support must evolve over time. Because dementia is progressive, participants emphasised the importance of continually reassessing travellers' needs, capabilities, and preferences.

This finding advances existing tourism and ageing research (Wen et al., 2022) by highlighting adaptability as a core principle of inclusive tourism practice. Rather than viewing accessibility as static, the findings

suggest that inclusive tourism should be understood as an ongoing negotiation between travellers, care partners, and service providers.

Destination management organisations (DMOs) and tourism operators must understand these challenges and drivers to develop strategic solutions and innovations that meet the needs of an ageing population (Patterson & Balderas-Cejudo, 2023). The theme of *fostering bonds and purpose* recognises the central role of families as a consideration for travel plans and as a motivation for travel, both for those living with dementia and their care partners (Vega-Vazquez et al., 2021; Patterson & Balderas-Cejudo, 2023). Travel was valued not only for leisure, but also for maintaining relationships, identity, and emotional well-being. These findings reinforce prior studies identifying the emotional, cognitive, and social benefits of tourism participation for people living with dementia and their carers (Vega-Vazquez et al., 2021; Innes et al., 2021). The theme of *travel as a key factor to living well* acknowledges that travel often remains important to individuals even after a dementia diagnosis (Connell & Page, 2020; Field et al., 2021). However, the diagnosis alters the travel dynamic. Participants acknowledged that unfamiliar environments, disrupted routines, stigma, and limited staff awareness can reduce confidence and discourage travel (Connell & Page, 2019; Field et al., 2021). The findings therefore illustrate the tension between the therapeutic value of travel and the practical barriers that may exclude people with dementia from tourism experiences. Effective strategies are therefore essential to counter and overcome these barriers and help people with dementia and their carers fulfill their travel aspirations.

To address the second research question, the findings indicate that dementia-inclusive tourism currently operates through fragmented and uneven support structures. Most services remain small-scale, locally driven, and dependent on a limited number of dedicated individuals. While initiatives such as the Sunflower Scheme have improved awareness and accessibility, broader implementation across tourism systems remains limited. The study contributes theoretically by conceptualising dementia-inclusive tourism as a spectrum of support. At one end, there are low-intervention initiatives that assist with navigation and communication during travel; at the other are fully managed holidays providing comprehensive care and supervision. Between these extremes are varying levels of formal and informal support, including companions and care partners. This spectrum framework extends existing dementia and tourism scholarship by demonstrating that inclusion is not binary, but instead varies according to travellers' evolving capabilities, support networks, and travel contexts.

4.1. Theoretical contributions

This study advances dementia and tourism scholarship by reframing the push–pull model (Crompton, 1979) to explain the evolving nature of travel for people living with dementia and their care partners. Traditional applications of the push–pull model conceptualise pull factors as attractive destination attributes that

encourage travel participation. However, this study extends the model by reframing pull factors as forces that increasingly constrain dementia-related travel participation, including cognitive decline, physical limitations and logistical complexity (Peterson et al., 2020; Peterson et al., 2024). Conversely, push factors are reconceptualised as enabling factors that sustain participation despite these constraints, including training, advocacy, social support, stimulation, and opportunities for physical activity (Vega-Vazquez et al., 2021; Wen et al., 2022; Patterson & Balderas-Cejudo, 2023). Figure 1 visualises these dynamics through the metaphor of a seesaw, illustrating how pull factors operate as constraining forces on dementia-related travel, while push factors function as counterbalancing supports and enabling mechanisms that sustain travel participation over time, as identified by travel experts.

Like all metaphors, the seesaw model is not perfect, nor is it meant to be representative of the scale of the challenges people living with dementia face. Unlike conventional tourism models that assume relatively stable motivations and destination preferences, the findings indicate that both constraints and enabling supports shift over time, requiring ongoing reassessment and adaptation of travel practices and services. Specialist service providers emphasised that strategies effective for one individual may be unsuitable for another, highlighting the highly personalised and evolving nature of dementia-related travel. Consequently, dementia-inclusive tourism is conceptualised not as a fixed accessibility outcome, but as a relational and adaptive process shaped by changing needs and capacities. By integrating perspectives from tourism, health, and social care, the model offers an interdisciplinary framework for understanding how personalised support, advocacy, and flexible service provision can sustain quality of life and ongoing tourism participation for people living with dementia and their care partners.

Figure 1. Seesaw dynamics of travel for people living well with dementia and their care partners

Note. The seesaw illustrates the dynamic balance between constraining factors (above the bar) and enabling factors and positive outcomes (below the bar). When enabling supports are strong, the benefits of travel can outweigh the challenges, promoting participation and quality of life.

4.2. Practical implications

Although tourism operators are increasingly recognising the importance of dementia-inclusive travel, implementation remains uneven due to limited resources, insufficient staff training, and inadequate accessible infrastructure (Page & Connell, 2024). The findings highlight the need for multi-level responses across intrapersonal, interpersonal, and structural dimensions (Innes et al., 2016). Intrapersonal strategies include additional travel time, careful planning, and continual reassessment of travellers' changing needs. Interpersonal approaches emphasise staff training, partnerships, and support networks that strengthen dementia awareness and service responsiveness (Blanas et al., 2016; Connell & Page, 2019). Structural responses involve accessible infrastructure, clear signage, supportive environmental cues, and affordable services (Mathews et al., 2021; Warren et al., 2022). Participants also identified advocacy initiatives, such as the Sunflower Scheme, in reducing stigma and improving recognition of non-visible disabilities. Collectively, the findings suggest that dementia-inclusive tourism cannot rely on standardised accessibility measures alone, but requires flexible, person-centred approaches that adapt to changing needs over time.

The findings also generate practical implications for tourism businesses, DMOs and policymakers. For tourism operators, dementia-inclusive practice requires more than basic accessibility compliance; it demands dementia-awareness training, flexible service delivery, clear communication, and personalised support for travellers with dementia and their care partners. Collaboration with healthcare professionals and community organisations may further strengthen the design of dementia-inclusive experiences. For DMOs, the findings demonstrate the importance of accessible information, inclusive visitor infrastructure, and cross-sector partnerships in positioning destinations as dementia-inclusive. DMOs may also play an important role in promoting dementia-inclusive standards and increasing awareness of this growing market segment (Patterson et al., 2021). From a policy perspective, the findings suggest a need for greater recognition of dementia-inclusive tourism within health and tourism policy frameworks. Policymakers could support the development of guidelines, accreditation schemes, staff training initiatives, and funding opportunities that encourage inclusive tourism practices. Integrating dementia-inclusive tourism into broader healthy ageing and accessible tourism strategies may also help improve quality of life and social participation for people living with dementia and their care partners.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study contributes to the growing literature on dementia-inclusive tourism by examining the perspectives of travel experts who support the travel aspirations of people living with dementia and their care partners. The findings reinforce the broader concept of living well with dementia by demonstrating how travel can support social connection, stimulation, physical well-being, relaxation, and quality of life. Thematic analysis identified four interconnected themes: enabling tourism services, the logistics of enabling support, fostering bonds and purpose, and travel as a contributor to living well. Collectively, the findings highlight that dementia-inclusive tourism depends on flexible, person-centred approaches characterised by tailored communication, structured planning and ongoing support throughout the travel experience. The study also highlights the need for more inclusive tourism practices across the tourism, hospitality and community sectors to better support this growing and often overlooked traveller segment.

This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the COVID-19 pandemic affected the scope and timing of data collection, with travel restrictions and reduced tourism activity limiting participant access and potentially influencing how participants reflected on travel experiences and service provision during a period of significant industry disruption. Second, all participants were based in the UK and USA, where dementia-inclusive tourism initiatives are comparatively more established, which may limit the transferability of findings to destinations with different policy, healthcare and tourism contexts.

Nevertheless, the study provides exploratory insights that may inform the development of dementia-inclusive practices in emerging destinations where such services remain limited or absent. Third, the findings are based solely on the perspectives of service providers, which may introduce professional or organisational bias, particularly as participants may emphasise the value and effectiveness of the services they deliver. While provider perspectives offer important practical insights into service delivery and operational challenges, they do not fully capture the lived experiences of people living with dementia and their care partners. Future research should therefore adopt participatory and co-design approaches that directly involve people living with dementia, care partners, and clinicians to provide a more comprehensive and balanced understanding of dementia-inclusive travel experiences across different stages of dementia and diverse tourism settings.

Declaration of Research and Publication Ethics

Anja Pabel, Maria O'Reilly, Pamela Meredith, and Lee-Fay Low declare that this study does not require ethics committee approval. The research was conducted in compliance with national and international research and publication ethics

Author Contribution Rate Statement

Conceptualization: A.P., M. O'R, P. M. L-F.L.; Methodology: A.P., M. O'R, P. M. L-F.L.; Formal Analysis: A. P. M. O'R.; Writing – Original Draft: A. P. M. O'R.; Writing – Review & Editing: A. P. M. O'R. P. M. L.L. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Declaration of Conflict of Interest

Anja Pabel, Maria O'Reilly, Pamela Meredith, Lee-Fay Low declares no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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Data Availability Statement

The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Usage Declaration

Anja Pabel, Maria O'Reilly, Pamela Meredith, and Lee-Fay Low used ChatGPT, CoPilot and Grammarly solely for ChatGPT was used to create Figure 1 and for clarity of expressions and readability. The author(s) assume full responsibility for the factual accuracy and originality of the final content.

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